

EDITORIAL

Message from the Editor-in-Chief of
International Journal of Science Annals, 2024

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Background and
Aim of Study:

Abstract

The publication of scientific papers in the media is becoming more and more accessible. This creates competition between scientific journals. It can ensure an increase in the scientific level of published products.

The aim of the study: to familiarise both the readers and the authors with the activities of the International Journal of Science Annals (IJSA).

Results:

The results of the journal's activities over the past year and its future prospects were analysed. Authors were informed about the benefits of publishing in the IJSA and about the possibility of participating in international scientific events (conferences, competitions) organised with the participation of the journal.

Conclusions:

The high competition in the publishing market requires the IJSA to systematically improve the scientific level of the journal, to adhere to high publishing standards and ethical norms, to create coordinated, productive relationships between authors and reviewers, and to provide them with new opportunities.

Keywords:

publishing standards, journal, guidelines, peer review process, scientific events

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Introduction

Scientific publications are the most effective way to share your research with the relevant experts and the general public.

The popularity of a particular journal among readers is determined by interest in its content and accessibility. While the popularity of a journal among authors is often due to its brand and its inclusion in certain scientometric databases.

International scientometric databases, repositories and search engines, as well as free and open access to scientific research, have created favourable conditions for authors to disseminate their ideas to colleagues and society. This has removed a number of constraints (availability, scope of distribution, number of copies, cost, etc.).

Results

Analysis of the Journal Activity

A book, journal or other type of printed (paper) publication, as a material phenomenon of human culture, is increasingly likely to cease to exist in the future as it is converted to an electronic format.

Long-established journals have already registered and are publishing online versions of their issues today. However, they still continue to publish print versions. Maybe it is because of the registration obligations. But one would hope that the cultural traditions and ethical principles of publishers are the reason for this. The IJSA has print and online ISSNs. Printed copies are sent to leading libraries and universities. It has a positive impact on the author's citation index and the university's position in international rankings.

The IJSA has a highly qualified team of reviewers. The website provides a set of mandatory criteria for manuscript evaluation. Response form templates developed for authors. Authors can appeal against reviews and the editor's decision. The IJSA Editorial Board includes the most authoritative scientists in the fields of Education, Psychology and Medicine from 17 countries and 5 continents. We guarantee compliance with the appropriate level of publication ethics and copyright protection at all stages of material review. The IJSA is a member of the Committee of Publication Ethics (COPE, 2024).

The IJSA Editorial Office is very strict about plagiarism. The Journal offers three levels of plagiarism checking for a manuscript. The first level is carried out by the author when submitting the manuscript. The second level is carried out by the editorial staff. The third level can be carried out by the reader if similarities are detected. For this purpose, the website has a "Submit an appeal against plagiarism" function.

The IJSA has a sophisticated, multi-functional website that provides authors with access to paper templates and supporting documents. The website also has personal pages for each of the authors.

In 2023, the Editorial Office received 119 manuscripts, of which: 14 were published, 105 were rejected. The average number of rejected manuscripts is 85%, of which: 40% are rejected during the preliminary evaluation process; 45% are rejected during the peer review process. We have considered the issue of quality and quantity of scientific publications (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2021).

The IJSA is represented at universities and in more than 160 libraries around the world. Present in over 40 international scientometric databases, repositories and search engines.

Future Journal Activity Directions

KRPOCH Publishing and the Editorial Board take into account current trends in scientific publishing (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023; Pypenko, 2023), based on which the journal development plan for the next 5 years has been developed.

KRPOCH Publishing, in collaboration with the IJSA, organises annual international scientific conferences on Current Issues of Education and Science, and Psychological and Pedagogical Problems of Modern Specialist Formation. At conferences, all authors are invited to present a report. IJSA authors pay no registration fee to attend these scientific events and have the opportunity to present their research to all conference participants. In addition, the authors' presentations are

available in open access on the official YouTube channel of the KRPOCH conferences.

KRPOCH Publishing organises annual scientific competitions, including International Competition Mental Health in the Digital Society (ICMHDS-2024). KRPOCH Publishing covers the full cost of publishing manuscripts submitted to the competition in the IJSA. It motivates young researchers.

Papers focusing on digitalisation and the use of artificial intelligence in education and medicine are a priority for the current issue of IJSA.

In January 2024, the IJSA has been submitted for a pre-evaluation report for inclusion in Scopus and for evaluation by the Web of Science editorial team (status – under evaluation).

Conclusions

The IJSA adheres to high publishing standards and ethical norms. The journal combines the requirements of the reviewers and the views of the authors. The journal organises international events where it creates and provides a platform to promote the ideas of IJSA authors. Despite all the difficulties that the KRPOCH Publishing house and the IJSA Office have experienced in connection with the military aggression against Ukraine, we continue to move forward.

References

- COPE. (n. d.). *International Journal of Science Annals* [COPE Members page]. <https://publicationethics.org/members/international-journal-science-annals>
- Kharkiv Regional Public Organization "Culture of Health". (2024). *International competition "Mental Health in the Digital Society" (ICMHDS-2024)*. <https://doi.org/10.26697/competitions.icmhds>
- Melnyk, Yu. B., & Pypenko, I. S. (2021). Dilemma: Quality or quantity in scientific periodical publishing. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 4(2), 5–7. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijisa.2021.2.1>
- Melnyk, Yu. B., & Pypenko, I. S. (2023). The legitimacy of artificial intelligence and the role of ChatBots in scientific publications. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 6(1), 5–10. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijisa.2023.1.1>
- Pypenko, I. S. (2023). Human and artificial intelligence interaction. *International Journal of Science Annals*, 6(2), 54–56. <https://doi.org/10.26697/ijisa.2023.2.7>

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